

METHODOLOGY FOR PREPARING ELEMENTARY STUDENTS FOR PIRLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT CONTROL

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1st stage master

Abstract: This article examines the ways of preparing junior schoolchildren for PIRLS assignments in literary reading lessons in primary grades. The essence of the international research PIRLS, a comparative analysis of educational systems of different countries and the exchange of experience to improve the quality of reading and understanding of the text by junior schoolchildren of Uzbekistan are revealed. The article pays attention to the importance of developing reading skills, understanding the text and the specificity of mastering this skill by students for further education in high school.

Keywords: reading skill, recoding, technical and semantic side of reading, PIRLS, analysis, international research, information search, value judgment, PIRLS structure, interactive tasks, speech development.

Reading is one of the most important types of speech activity, closely related to both pronunciation and understanding of speech. Also, "reading" is the ability to perceive and understand information recorded (transmitted) in one way or another, it can be reproduced by technical devices. This is the process of recoding the signs seen and the ratio of its sound and understanding. In the process of reading, two sides can be identified: technical (the way of reading, correctness, expressiveness, speed (pace) of reading) and semantic (understanding and assimilation of the text). Between these two sides There is a close, inextricable connection between the reading process. Considering the above, the technical side of the reading skill includes articulatory development, and the main purpose of the reading process is demonstrated by its semantic side. It is the development of the skill of semantic understanding of the text that is an assessment of the acquisition of a full-fledged reading skill. The international PIRLS study was created to identify the development of the semantic and technical side of reading. But PIRLS puts more emphasis on the semantic side of the skill. The requirements and standards in education are increasing every day. To keep up with the over, time and with modern standards, many countries pay great attention to this factor. For example, the comparative analysis of PIRLS meets all the requirements of modern research on the skill of

reading and understanding text. PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literature Study) is an international comparative study of the quality of reading and understanding of text for 4th grade students, which is conducted under the guidance of the International Association for the Assessment of Academic Achievements IEA. PIRLS considers two types of reading – reading is designed to achieve the skill of literary reading and reading for mastering and applying information. For control, students are given two works, one of which is a popular science text, and the second is an artistic one. The result of mastering the information is the students' answers to the submitted tasks related to the text. The tasks for the texts consider four skills - information retrieval, the ability to draw conclusions, explanation and synthesis of information, analysis and value judgment of the content, specificity the language structures of the text. In this study, knowledge is considered students graduating from the fourth grade of primary school, because, namely, the fourth year of study is a necessary stage in the development of children. Reading is a skill that is not only a narrow meaning of the manifestation of this meaning, but also a skill on which the well-being of children's education in other subjects depends.

The structure of PIRLS is that students are given 10 test alternatives as a task. These texts are intended for the comprehensive formation and development of the student's speech. In general, 4 literary texts were used in the study: "Inverted mice", "A piece of clay", "Flowers on the roof", "The Hare warns of an earthquake"; 3 popular science texts: "Leonardo da Vinci", "Nights of dead Ends", "Antarctica"; and the text "Along the route along rivers", which include various forms of information presentation. All test variants had the same

the structure and degree of difficulty. All types of the test consisted of two parts, each of which gave one text and from 11 to 14 tasks to the text. The work was given 80 minutes, 40 minutes for each part. The questions do not assume the standard appearance of the test, but with creative tasks and tests requiring a complete answer, in search of which the student must refer to the text every time and use logical thinking, memory and value judgment. This, in turn, develops skills such as identifying separately isolated information that is given in the text; the ability to do conclusions from the information received; to comment on and combine individual information of the text; the ability to assess the essence, the image of the language, the type of both the whole message and individual information. Tasks involve the development of speech and skills to draw an analogy, to contrast information obtained from the text, to practically use the knowledge and information obtained, the development of value judgment, that is, to determine the author's message, his

main theme of the work, the artistic means that the author used when creating his work, the assessment of the plausibility of the situation of the phenomena described. From all that has been said, the need to change the pedagogical position and pedagogical communication directly follows. Success does not depend so much on how well and interestingly the teacher presents the material. The main resource of development is the experience of reading, listening and discussing, the experience of one's own and others' mistakes and victories.

Pedagogical requirements of speech development through PIRLS tasks: orientation to ensuring the construction of the content of the educational subject, taking into account the orientation to self-knowledge, self-development of personality based on a competence-based approach, the implementation of which takes place through the main content component of the subject - an educational task aimed at forming the ability to solve standard educational tasks, as well as tasks of interaction with society based mainly on practice-oriented knowledge (data, information, scientific concepts, instructions, skills in working with tables, graphs, interpretation and collection of information). The use of innovative teaching technologies by a teacher to organize independent activities of students, initiating independence in determining goals, planning and awareness of their own actions.

REFERENCES

1. Azimov Y., Babaeva S. Use of innovative technologies in lessons of writing in primary classes //Bridge to science: research works. – 2019.
2. Baymuradovna B. S. et al. Pedagogical technologies for the development of cognitive creative abilities of students in the lessons of the Russian language //Journal of Critical Reviews. – 2020.
3. Babaeva Sh. B. The role of the media in teaching Russian in national groups //A young scientist. - 2018.
4. Babaeva Sh. B. The role of the media in teaching Russian in national schools, groups //A young scientist. - 2018.
5. H. Bakieva. Formation of literary analysis skills in 4th grade reading lessons. Educational-methodological manual. - T.: Nodirabegim. 2021.
6. M. Umarova and b. Reading book. Textbook for Grade 3. - T.: Teacher. 2019.